

Highlights

Correction of Accidental Coincidences in Four-Channel Counting Systems: A Method for G-TDCR Measurements

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- Analytical correction of accidental coincidences for a 4-detector counter.
- Method described and validated on datasets under varied conditions.
- Agreement evaluated against an experimental correction method.
- Simple equations enable direct use in accidental-sensitive methods.

Correction of Accidental Coincidences in Four-Channel Counting Systems: A Method for G-TDCR Measurements

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ABSTRACT

Accidental coincidences can significantly bias coincidence-counting measurements when high count rates, multiple detection channels and long coincidences windows are involved. This issue is particularly important for the development of multiple coincidence detector system and especially for the Compton-TDCR methods used in ionizing radiation metrology and also in our case in scintillator metrology, where a gamma detector is combined with the conventional three-photomultiplier TDCR system. In this work, we address the correction of accidental coincidences in a four-detector coincidence configuration (one gamma channel and three photon channels using photomultiplier tubes) based on triple-to-double coincidence technique.

To ensure accurate correction of measured counting rates, we present and compare two complementary approaches: (i) an experimental correction method, and (ii) a new analytical correction method based on simple equations that are straightforward to implement in data-processing routines. The analytical formalism is developed for the four-detector case and is designed to be readily extended to coincidence systems with N detectors.

The proposed equations were evaluated on several coincidence measurement datasets representative of different measurement conditions. The results demonstrate the validity and good performance of the analytical correction, while also confirming the robustness of the experimental approach. These developments provide practical tools for improved coincidence correction in multi-detector systems and support the reliable implementation of Compton-TDCR methods in metrological applications.

1. Introduction

Coincidence counting is a foundational technique in radiation detection and nuclear measurements, historically used to identify correlated emissions and establish nuclear disintegration schemes. Early methodological developments and reviews already highlighted the distinction between true and accidental coincidences and the central role of timing in coincidence measurements Mitchell (1948). In radionuclide metrology, these principles were formalized in primary standardization through high-efficiency $4\pi\beta\text{-}\gamma$ coincidence methods, notably in the works of Campion and of Houtermans and Miguel Campion (1959); Houtermans and Miguel (1962). The method is today widely used in many coincidence cases for radionuclide metrology Collé (2009) and accidental coincidences should be corrected. However, most cases were solved using anti-coincidence techniques.

Within liquid scintillation counting, the triple-to-double coincidence ratio (TDCR) method extends coincidence principles to a three-photomultiplier configuration and has become a major method for radionuclide standardization Broda (2003). More recently, we introduced and compared analytical and experimental approaches for correcting accidental coincidences in TDCR measurements Dutsov et al. (2020), and then examined the impact of the coincidence resolving time on TDCR activity calculations Dutsov et al. (2021). This work provides a strong basis for extending

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accidental-coincidence corrections to multi-detector configurations especially for pure beta-emitter. In recent work, we aimed to develop a primary method that does not rely on efficiency modelling such as the TDCR method, which led to the development of the Compton-TDCR method. Accordingly, the objective of the present work Sabot et al. (2024) is twofold: (1) to establish a new primary method, in particular for radionuclides with no practical coincidence emissions, such as pure beta emitters and low-energy electron-capture emitters; and (2) to develop the tools required for refined metrology of scintillator responses.

The Compton-TDCR is based on the combination of three photomultiplier tubes (PMT) and one gamma detector. The method requires individual counting channels for each detector and a specific electronics to apply extendable dead time to single channels and to record coincidences between two channels (double coincidences), three channels (triple coincidences) or four channels (quadruple coincidences).

One limitation of the present method lies in the reliance on scintillation events recorded in coincidence with an energy deposition arising from a Compton interaction of the incident gamma beam to infer the quantity of interest. Because the probability of this process is low and the associated events are difficult to detect, a high incident photon flux is required. This results in high single-channel counting rates, whereas the number of physically relevant coincidence events remains low.

With the previous mini-TDCR device Sabot et al. (2022), experimental and analytical methods were compared to correct random coincidences Dutsov et al. (2020); however, these corrections were limited to three PMTs. With the new Compton-TDCR device Sabot et al. (2024), it is necessary to expand the method to 4-channel configuration or more. In this work, we therefore present both an experimental correction approach and a new analytical method based on simple equations for four-detector coincidence systems, which can be easily extended to N -channels.

2. Materials and methods

Experimental accidental coincidence correction.

Before the development of an analytical method, an experimental accidental coincidence correction method was applied by Sabot et al. (2024) with the Compton-TDCR device. This method requires the use of multiple long coincidence windows measurements to evaluate the accidental rate, such as 2000 ns and 2500 ns. For short coincidence window, the data contains true and accidental coincidences, but for a very long coincidence window, true coincidence are dominated by accidental coincidences. Therefore, the true counting rate $N_t^{(i)}(\tau)$ in the i^{th} channel for a coincidence window τ is calculated as:

$$N_t^{(i)}(\tau) = N_m^{(i)}(\tau) - \left(\frac{N_m^{(i)}(\tau_2) - N_m^{(i)}(\tau_1)}{\tau_2 - \tau_1} \right) \tau, \quad (1)$$

with $N_m^{(i)}(\tau)$, the measured counting rate in the i^{th} channel for a coincidence window τ . τ_1 and τ_2 are coincidence windows in ns and are chosen large enough assuming that after a certain coincidence window, the counting rate doesn't increase. This experimental method assumes that, beyond a given coincidence time window, the counting rate remains constant. This assumption appears reasonable, since any scintillator—provided it does not exhibit afterglow—is characterized by a finite decay time constant; for a given number of produced photons, the signal eventually decreases to the noise level. To validate this assumption, time difference distribution for DG event in the compton-TDCR system with a vial of 20 mL of UltimaGold® scintillator is plotted in Fig. 1 and shows that for long resolving time (2000 - 2500 ns), events are uncorrelated.

In a standard electronics setups, such as Bouchard and Cassette (2000) or Jordanov et al. (2020), this setting may not be achievable due either a fixed coincidence window or a narrow range of variation bellow some hundred of ns, making this method impossible to use. Nevertheless, it is feasible using a CAEN digitizer that outputs list-mode data containing the time-stamped information of each event. A dedicated post-treatment software, was developed to apply different analysis type on the list-mode data obtained from CAEN analyser specifically to implement dead-time and coincidence window logic on a four channel system.. In the document, this method is identified as experimental method and thus used to be compared with the analytical approach developed in this work.

Analytical approach.

Based on the method explained by Dutsov et al. (2020), we can distinguish each individual and coincidence channels with \wedge the "and" operator and \vee the "or" operator for 4 channels as:

- 3 single PMT event channels (A, B, C) and 1 single gamma event channel (G);
- 3 double PMT coincidence channels ($AB = A \wedge B$, $BC = B \wedge C$, $AC = A \wedge C$), the logical sum of the double coincidences channel ($D = AB \vee BC \vee AC$) and 3 double gamma-PMT coincidence channels ($AG = A \wedge G$, $BG = B \wedge G$, $CG = C \wedge G$);
- 1 triple PMT coincidence channel ($T = ABC = A \wedge B \wedge C$), 3 triple gamma-PMT coincidence channels ($ABG = A \wedge B \wedge G$, $BCG = B \wedge C \wedge G$, $ACG = A \wedge C \wedge G$) and the logical sum of triple gamma-PMT coincidences channel ($DG = ABG \vee BCG \vee ACG$);
- 1 quadruple gamma-PMT coincidence channel ($TG = ABCG = A \wedge B \wedge C \wedge G$).

To illustrate these physical and logical channels, Fig. 2 presents the correspondence between the classical three-circle Venn diagram used in TDCR logic and the triangular representation adopted in this work. Individual channels are mapped to the triangle vertices, double coincidences to edge midpoints, and the triple coincidence to the center of the triangular face. This 2D representation is suitable for a three-channel system, whereas a four-channel system requires a 3D representation. As shown in Fig. 3, the four-channel logic can be represented by a tetrahedron, with the quadruple coincidence located at its center.

The analytical method details the exact formulas for calculating accidental coincidence rates in a 4-channel system but the methodology can be applied for a N -channel system. It is based on the probability of uncorrelated events within a coincidence window.

In the following sections, we will use the notation defined below:

- Physical channel rate (n_L): Raw counting rate derived from the list-mode data for logic L . This rate is inclusive (contains higher ranks). E.g., n_{AB} includes events ABC , ABG , and $ABCG$.
- Pure rate (p_X): Rate of events occurring exclusively in the set X and nowhere else. This rate is exclusive. E.g., p_{AB} triggers A and B but not C or G.
- Target rate for logic L (t_L): Sum of all pure rates that satisfy the logic $L \rightarrow t_L = \sum_{X \in S_L} p_X$ which is inclusive (derived from (p_X)).

The approach proposed by Dutsov et al. (2020) for accidental-coincidence correction consists in first estimating the exclusive (pure) rates of statistically independent events (e.g., $p_A, p_B, p_C, p_{AB}, \dots$) and then using these rates to derive corrections for the measured physical logic channels. This approach is doable for a three-channel system. However, when extended to four channels, the combination complexity increases substantially because of the large number of crossed terms. For example, for the AB channel, one must account not only for $T (= ABC)$ but also for ABG and $ABCG$, which leads to many coupled terms and makes direct derivation difficult to handle in practice.

To generalize the method to an N -channel system, a step-wise formulation is preferable. The first step is an inclusion–exclusion decomposition, i.e. the computation of the exclusive (pure) rates p_X from the measured inclusive rates n_L (from rank N down to rank 1). The second step is the logic-level accidental model: for each physical logic L (e.g., AB, T, D, \dots), the accidental correction $Corr_L$ is computed. This term corresponds to the accidental coincidence rate to be subtracted from the measured channel n_L . It is derived from the set of pure rates $\{p_X\}$ using two contributions: Type-1 (creation term) defined by Jánossy (1944) and Type-2 (pile-up term). Finally, the corrected rate is obtained as:

$$n_L^{\text{corr}} = n_L - Corr_L. \quad (2)$$

For the present four-channel system, the pure rates can be obtained from the measured inclusive rates by inclusion–exclusion, as given in Eq. 3. For example, the $ABCG$ rate is exclusive by definition, hence $p_{ABCG} = n_{ABCG}$. The

measured inclusive rate n_{ABC} contains contributions from both ABC and $ABCG$, so that $p_{ABC} = n_{ABC} - n_{ABCG}$.

Quadruple p_{ABCG} :

$$p_{ABCG} = n_{ABCG}$$

Triples $p_{ABC}, p_{ABG}, p_{BCG}, p_{ACG}$:

$$p_{ABC} = n_{ABC} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{ABG} = n_{ABG} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{BCG} = n_{BCG} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{ACG} = n_{ACG} - n_{ABCG}$$

(3)

The same reasoning applies to all lower-order channels such as double and single Eq. 4. For instance, the pure rate AB occurs in the counting rates AB, ABC, ABG and $ABCG$, but $ABCG$ is included within ABC and ABG . If p_{AB} defined as the counting rate of pure AB is the rate difference of $AB - ABC - ABG$, it means that it subtracts twice the counting rate of $ABCG$; therefore, the rate $ABCG$ must be added to this difference.

Doubles $p_{AB}, p_{BC}, p_{AC}, p_{AG}, p_{BG}, p_{CG}$:

$$p_{AB} = n_{AB} - n_{ABC} - n_{ABG} + n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{BC} = n_{BC} - n_{ABC} - n_{BCG} + n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{AC} = n_{AC} - n_{ABC} - n_{ACG} + n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{AG} = n_{AG} - n_{ABG} - n_{ACG} + n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{BG} = n_{BG} - n_{ABG} - n_{BCG} + n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_{CG} = n_{CG} - n_{BCG} - n_{ACG} + n_{ABCG}$$

(4)

Singles p_A, p_B, p_C, p_G :

$$p_A = n_A - n_{AB} + n_{ABC} + n_{ABG} - n_{AC} + n_{ACG} - n_{AG} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_B = n_B - n_{AB} + n_{ABC} + n_{ABG} - n_{BC} + n_{BCG} - n_{BG} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_C = n_C - n_{AC} + n_{ABC} + n_{ACG} - n_{BC} + n_{BCG} - n_{CG} - n_{ABCG}$$

$$p_G = n_G - n_{AG} + n_{ABG} + n_{ACG} - n_{BG} + n_{BCG} - n_{CG} - n_{ABCG}$$

Once the system is decomposed into pure rates (p_X), the accidental correction for each physical logic L (AB, T, D, \dots) can be computed using type 1 and 2 contributions.

The standard TDCR model relies on the assumption that each recorded count corresponds to a single disintegration (Poisson process). To preserve this, the Eq. 5 from Jánosy (1944) is applied for the rate of 2 accidental coincidences,

$$N_a = 2\tau(N_1N_2), \quad (5)$$

where N_a is the rate of accidental coincidences, τ is the coincidence resolving time and N_1 and N_2 are the count rates of two statistically independent (uncorrelated) sources. This factor 2 arises from temporal symmetry: a coincidence is registered if event 1 opens the window and event 2 falls inside, or vice-versa. For any physical channel rate n_L , the total accidental rate is the sum of two distinct formation mechanisms:

$$Corr_L = Corr_L^{(1)} + Corr_L^{(2)}, \quad (6)$$

The creation contribution, $Corr_L^{(1)}$, (Type 1) occurs when two non-target, statistically independent events fall within the resolving time τ and their union satisfies the logic L . This contribution is time-symmetric and carries the factor 2 in Eq. 5. For example, the pure double p_{AB} is created when two uncorrelated singles p_A and p_B appear within the same coincidence window τ . This includes disjoint pairs (e.g. $p_{AB} + p_C \rightarrow p_{ABC}$) and overlapping pairs (e.g. $p_{AB} + p_{BC} \rightarrow p_{ABC}$).

The pile-up contribution, $Corr_L^{(2)}$, (Type 2) occurs when an event already satisfying logic L is recorded within a resolving-time window opened by another non-target event. In this case, the ordering is fixed (window opener first, target event second), and the factor 2 is not applied. To define the pile-up contribution, the total pure rate is:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{Total} &= \sum_{all} p_i \\
&= p_A + p_B + p_C + p_G + p_{AB} + p_{AC} + p_{BC} + p_{AG} + p_{BG} + p_{CG} \\
&\quad + p_{ABC} + p_{ABG} + p_{BCG} + p_{ACG} + p_{ABCG}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The pile-up rate is calculated as the interaction between the state L and the rest of the pure probabilities ($p_{Total} - t_L$). It corresponds to the probability of a target event t_L to appear with any other event except t_L within the coincidence resolving time window:

$$Corr_L^{(2)} = \tau (p_{Total} - t_L) t_L \quad \text{with} \quad t_L = \sum_{X \in S_L} p_X \tag{8}$$

To compute all corrected rates ($AB, \dots, ABC, \dots, ABCG$), the first step is to detail all of the target sums. These must be calculated as the sum of all the pure rates p_X that are contained in the logic L . For example, the targeted rates t_{AB} is the sum of all the pure rates that contribute p_{AB}, p_{ABC}, p_{ABG} and p_{ABCG} . So for each logic L , the target rates are calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
t_{AB} &= p_{AB} + p_{ABC} + p_{ABG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{AC} &= p_{AC} + p_{ABC} + p_{ACG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{BC} &= p_{BC} + p_{ABC} + p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{AG} &= p_{AG} + p_{ABG} + p_{ACG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{BG} &= p_{BG} + p_{ABG} + p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{CG} &= p_{CG} + p_{ACG} + p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{ABC} &= p_{ABC} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{ABG} &= p_{ABG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{BCG} &= p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{ACG} &= p_{ACG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{ABCG} &= p_{ABCG}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The Jánossy rule is then applied to all pairs of statistically independent non-target events whose union satisfies the target logic. For double channels (AB, BC, AC, AG, BG, CG), the required auxiliary rates are. For example, in the case of the logic AB , the accidental coincidence arises from the overlap of two uncorrelated sources: events containing A but not B ($A\bar{B}$) and B but not A ($\bar{B}A$). Consequently, the Janossy rule applies to the interaction between these subsets. The probability of $A\bar{B}$ corresponds to the sum of all pure rates that contain A while strictly excluding B , in this case: p_A, p_{AC}, p_{AG} and p_{ACG} :

$$\begin{aligned}
A\bar{B} &= p_A + p_{AC} + p_{AG} + p_{ACG}, & \bar{B}A &= p_B + p_{BC} + p_{BG} + p_{BCG} \\
A\bar{C} &= p_A + p_{AB} + p_{AG} + p_{ABG}, & \bar{C}A &= p_C + p_{BC} + p_{CG} + p_{BCG} \\
B\bar{C} &= p_B + p_{AB} + p_{BG} + p_{ABG}, & \bar{C}\bar{B} &= p_C + p_{AC} + p_{CG} + p_{ACG} \\
A\bar{G} &= p_A + p_{AB} + p_{AC} + p_{ABC}, & \bar{G}A &= p_G + p_{BG} + p_{CG} + p_{BCG} \\
B\bar{G} &= p_B + p_{AB} + p_{BC} + p_{ABC}, & \bar{G}\bar{B} &= p_G + p_{AG} + p_{CG} + p_{ACG} \\
C\bar{G} &= p_C + p_{AC} + p_{BC} + p_{ABC}, & \bar{G}\bar{C} &= p_G + p_{AG} + p_{BG} + p_{ABG}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Then, the correction rates are obtained as the sum of the two contributions, i.e. creation and pile-up. For example, for the AB channel, the creation term is calculated by means of Janossy rule as show in Eq. 5 between $A\bar{B}$ and $\bar{B}A$

and the pile-up term is calculated as Eq. 8 applied to t_{AB} . Finally, the correction terms of double channels are:

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{AB} &= 2\tau(\overline{AB})(\overline{BA}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{AB})t_{AB} \\
Corr_{AC} &= 2\tau(\overline{AC})(\overline{CA}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{AC})t_{AC} \\
Corr_{BC} &= 2\tau(\overline{BC})(\overline{CB}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{BC})t_{BC} \\
Corr_{AG} &= 2\tau(\overline{AG})(\overline{GA}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{AG})t_{AG} \\
Corr_{BG} &= 2\tau(\overline{BG})(\overline{GB}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{BG})t_{BG} \\
Corr_{CG} &= 2\tau(\overline{CG})(\overline{GC}) + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{CG})t_{CG}
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

For the triple-coincidence channels (ABC , ABG , ACG , BCG), the creation term must account for a larger set of statistically independent event pairs than for doubles channel. For example, for the ABC logic, accidental formation can arise from single–double combinations (e.g. AB with C , BC with A , AC with B) as well as from double–double combinations (e.g. AB with AC , AB with BC , AC with BC). Consequently, the rates associated with all relevant independent pairs must be explicitly evaluated. As an example, the probability of $AB \cdot \overline{C}$ is the sum of all pure rates in all logic channels that contains AB but not C : p_{AB} and p_{ABG} . Then, as for the doubles, the correction factors of triples are calculated as the sum of the creation and pile-up contributions. The equations for ABC are developed:

$$\begin{aligned}
A \cdot \overline{BC} &= p_A + p_{AG} \\
B \cdot \overline{AC} &= p_B + p_{BG} \\
C \cdot \overline{AB} &= p_C + p_{CG} \\
AB \cdot \overline{C} &= p_{AB} + p_{ABG} \\
BC \cdot \overline{A} &= p_{BC} + p_{BCG} \\
AC \cdot \overline{B} &= p_{AC} + p_{ACG} \\
AB \cdot \overline{AC} &= p_{AB} + p_{ABG} = \overline{ABC} \\
AC \cdot \overline{AB} &= p_{AC} + p_{ACG} = \overline{ACB} \\
AB \cdot \overline{BC} &= p_{AB} + p_{ABG} = \overline{ABC} \\
BC \cdot \overline{AB} &= p_{BC} + p_{BCG} = \overline{BCA} \\
AC \cdot \overline{BC} &= p_{AC} + p_{ACG} = \overline{ACB} \\
BC \cdot \overline{AC} &= p_{BC} + p_{BCG} = \overline{BCA}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{ABC} &= 2\tau \left[(AB \cdot \overline{C})(C \cdot \overline{AB}) + (BC \cdot \overline{A})(A \cdot \overline{BC}) + (AC \cdot \overline{B})(B \cdot \overline{AC}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (AB \cdot \overline{AC})(AC \cdot \overline{AB}) + (AB \cdot \overline{BC})(BC \cdot \overline{AB}) + (AC \cdot \overline{BC})(BC \cdot \overline{AC}) \right] \\
&\quad + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{ABC})t_{ABC}.
\end{aligned}$$

The same procedure applies to the ABG logic channel:

$$\begin{aligned}
A \cdot \overline{BG} &= p_A + p_{AC} \\
B \cdot \overline{AG} &= p_B + p_{BC} \\
G \cdot \overline{AB} &= p_G + p_{CG} \\
AB \cdot \overline{G} &= p_{AB} + p_{ABC} = AB \cdot \overline{AG} = AB \cdot \overline{BG} \\
AG \cdot \overline{B} &= p_{AG} + p_{ACG} = AG \cdot \overline{AB} = AG \cdot \overline{BG} \\
BG \cdot \overline{A} &= p_{BG} + p_{BCG} = BG \cdot \overline{AB} = BG \cdot \overline{AG}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{ABG} &= 2\tau \left[(AB \cdot \overline{G})(G \cdot \overline{AB}) + (AG \cdot \overline{B})(B \cdot \overline{AG}) + (BG \cdot \overline{A})(A \cdot \overline{BG}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (AB \cdot \overline{AG})(AG \cdot \overline{AB}) + (AB \cdot \overline{BG})(BG \cdot \overline{AB}) + (AG \cdot \overline{BG})(BG \cdot \overline{AG}) \right] \\
&\quad + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{ABG})t_{ABG}
\end{aligned}$$

The same procedure applies to the ACG logic channel:

$$\begin{aligned}
A \cdot \overline{CG} &= p_A + p_{AB} \\
C \cdot \overline{AG} &= p_C + p_{BC} \\
G \cdot \overline{AC} &= p_G + p_{BG} \\
AC \cdot \overline{G} &= p_{AC} + p_{ABC} = AC \cdot \overline{AG} = AC \cdot \overline{CG} \\
AG \cdot \overline{C} &= p_{AG} + p_{ABG} = AG \cdot \overline{AC} = AG \cdot \overline{CG} \\
CG \cdot \overline{A} &= p_{CG} + p_{BCG} = CG \cdot \overline{AC} = CG \cdot \overline{AG}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{ACG} &= 2\tau \left[(AC \cdot \overline{G})(G \cdot \overline{AC}) + (AG \cdot \overline{C})(C \cdot \overline{AG}) + (CG \cdot \overline{A})(A \cdot \overline{CG}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (AC \cdot \overline{AG})(AG \cdot \overline{AC}) + (AC \cdot \overline{CG})(CG \cdot \overline{AC}) + (AG \cdot \overline{CG})(CG \cdot \overline{AG}) \right] \\
&\quad + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{ACG})t_{ACG}
\end{aligned}$$

And likewise for the BCG logic channel:

$$\begin{aligned}
B \cdot \overline{CG} &= p_B + p_{AB} \\
C \cdot \overline{BG} &= p_C + p_{AC} \\
G \cdot \overline{BC} &= p_G + p_{AG} \\
BC \cdot \overline{G} &= p_{BC} + p_{ABC} = BC \cdot \overline{BG} = BC \cdot \overline{CG} \\
BG \cdot \overline{C} &= p_{BG} + p_{ABG} = BG \cdot \overline{BC} = BG \cdot \overline{CG} \\
CG \cdot \overline{B} &= p_{CG} + p_{ACG} = CG \cdot \overline{BC} = CG \cdot \overline{BG}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{BCG} &= 2\tau \left[(BC \cdot \overline{G})(G \cdot \overline{BC}) + (BG \cdot \overline{C})(C \cdot \overline{BG}) + (CG \cdot \overline{B})(B \cdot \overline{CG}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (BC \cdot \overline{BG})(BG \cdot \overline{BC}) + (BC \cdot \overline{CG})(CG \cdot \overline{BC}) + (BG \cdot \overline{CG})(CG \cdot \overline{BG}) \right] \\
&\quad + \tau(p_{Total} - t_{BCG})t_{BCG}
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, for the quadruple-coincidence channel $ABCG$, the Jánosy rule must be applied to all independent event pairs whose union satisfies the four-channel logic (e.g. ABC with G , AB with CG , AG with BC , as well as triple–triple

combinations). Combining creation and pile-up contributions, the accidental correction rate is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_{ABCG} = 2\tau & \left[(p_{ABC}p_G + p_{ABG}p_C + p_{BCG}p_A + p_{ACG}p_B) \right. \\
& + (p_{AB}p_{CG} + p_{AC}p_{BG} + p_{AG}p_{BC}) \\
& + (p_{ABC}p_{ABG} + p_{ABC}p_{BCG} + p_{ABC}p_{ACG} + p_{ABG}p_{BCG} + p_{ABG}p_{ACG} + p_{BCG}p_{ACG}) \\
& + p_{ABC}(p_{AG} + p_{BG} + p_{CG}) + p_{ABG}(p_{AC} + p_{BC} + p_{CG}) \\
& \left. + p_{BCG}(p_{AB} + p_{AC} + p_{AG}) + p_{ACG}(p_{AB} + p_{BC} + p_{BG}) \right] \\
& + \tau (p_{Total} - p_{ABCG}) p_{ABCG}
\end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

In the field of metrology, the D counting rate represents the logical sum of all the double coincidences between PMTs ($D = AB \vee BC \vee AC$) and DG represents the logical sum of triple coincidences between PMTs and the gamma detector ($DG = D \vee G = ABG \vee BCG \vee ACG$). As they combine the different coincidences events, these counting rate are often used in the TDCR and C-TDCR devices. As for the other channels, the first step is to compute the target rates for D and DG :

$$\begin{aligned}
t_D &= p_{AB} + p_{AC} + p_{BC} + p_{ABC} + p_{ABG} + p_{ACG} + p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG} \\
t_{DG} &= p_{ABG} + p_{ACG} + p_{BCG} + p_{ABCG}
\end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The corresponding accidental-correction terms are:

$$\begin{aligned}
Corr_D &= 2\tau \left[(p_A + p_{AG})(p_B + p_{BG}) + (p_A + p_{AG})(p_C + p_{CG}) + (p_B + p_{BG})(p_C + p_{CG}) \right] \\
& + \tau (p_{Total} - t_D) t_D \\
Corr_{DG} &= 2\tau \left[(p_{AB} + p_{AC} + p_{BC} + p_{ABC})(p_G + p_{AG} + p_{BG} + p_{CG}) \right. \\
& + p_A(p_{BG} + p_{CG}) + p_B(p_{AG} + p_{CG}) + p_C(p_{AG} + p_{BG}) \\
& \left. + (p_{AG}p_{BG} + p_{AG}p_{CG} + p_{BG}p_{CG}) \right] \\
& + \tau (p_{Total} - t_{DG}) t_{DG}
\end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Finally, the last stage of the analytical approach is to subtract the accidental-correction rates from the raw counting rates. For example, the corrected counting rate of channel AB is obtained as $n_{AB}^{corr} = n_{AB} - Corr_{AB}$. The corrected rates are:

$$\begin{aligned}
n_{AB}^{corr} &= n_{AB} - Corr_{AB}, & n_{BC}^{corr} &= n_{BC} - Corr_{BC}, & n_{AC}^{corr} &= n_{AC} - Corr_{AC} \\
n_{AG}^{corr} &= n_{AG} - Corr_{AG}, & n_{BG}^{corr} &= n_{BG} - Corr_{BG}, & n_{CG}^{corr} &= n_{CG} - Corr_{CG} \\
n_D^{corr} &= n_D - Corr_D \\
n_{ABC}^{corr} &= n_{ABC} - Corr_{ABC}, & n_{ABG}^{corr} &= n_{ABG} - Corr_{ABG} \\
n_{BCG}^{corr} &= n_{BCG} - Corr_{BCG}, & n_{ACG}^{corr} &= n_{ACG} - Corr_{ACG} \\
n_{DG}^{corr} &= n_{DG} - Corr_{DG} \\
n_{ABCG}^{corr} &= n_{ABCG} - Corr_{ABCG}
\end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The methodology presented here is intended for N -channel coincidence systems that provide raw counting rates for single, double, triple, and higher-order logic channels, including both true and accidental coincidences. The present

formulation was verified against the three-channel TDCR expressions of Dutsov et al. (2020) and applied to a four-channel Compton-TDCR system. Since the analytical correction is derived from the measured rates and a user-defined resolving time, the choice of the coincidence window must balance the loss of true coincidences at too short τ against the increase of accidental coincidences at large τ . The experimental approach is less sensitive to this dependence but typically yields larger uncertainties because it relies on the statistics of time-difference distributions.

Experimental setup.

To compare the experimental (Expt.) and analytical (Calc.) corrections, three measurements were performed: one sample of 22 mL of UltimaGold[®] (UG) in polyethylene vial (PE-PTFE), and two ³H-in-UG (8 kBq and 21 kBq) with 10 mL of scintillator in a glass vials. Measurements were acquired using the portable Compton-TDCR device (Sabot et al., 2024). The Compton-TDCR setup combines three photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) with a CdTe detector used as the gamma channel, the sample is irradiated by a gamma-beam of 59.54 keV produced by a collimated and filtered ²⁴¹Am sealed source, giving 10 000 s⁻¹ event in the double count channel of the TDCR device. When using a scintillation sample without tritium, the recorded counting rates mainly originate from interactions of the incident gamma beam. When tritium is present, the observed rates include an additional contribution from beta decays in the sample. This additional contribution primarily affects the single-channel PMT rates, since tritium is a pure beta emitter and does not generate coincidences with the gamma detector. Consequently, the measured rates can be viewed as the superposition of a beam-induced component and a tritium-induced component, the latter contributing essentially PMTs singles and coincidences between PMTs. As a results it is a good way to test the accidental correction.

To amplify PMT signals and reduce electronic-noise impact, a $\times 10$ fast amplifier (750 MHz, from FastComTec) with 50 Ω input impedance was inserted in the PMT readout chain. Events were then digitized using a CAEN DT5751 digitizer operating in list mode, recording the energy and timestamp of each event in the four channels. In the present configuration, the constant-fraction discrimination (CFD) function from CAEN was used for timing, and the energy was collected using a 70 ns integration gate. The digitized data were processed offline using an in-house Rust software, which applies a user-defined dead time and coincidence resolving time to the four channels and computes the counting rates for each logic channel (*AB*, *AG*, ..., *ABC*, *ABG*, ..., *ABCG*). Channel-to-channel delays were adjusted to minimize systematic offsets in the time-difference distributions. For clarity of understanding in this study, we compare the results obtained across all channels combined. This approach provides greater clarity of results and, above all, a more significant statistical count.

As noted above, the Compton-TDCR device combines three photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) with an additional gamma detector. The PMT channels typically exhibit high single counting rates (10^3 – 10^4 s⁻¹), whereas the gamma channel is much lower (approximately 50 s⁻¹), resulting in low coincidence counting rates.

Moreover, the Compton-TDCR system developed at CEA is not intended solely for radionuclide metrology using standard liquid scintillators, but also for the characterization of new scintillators with longer decay times, such as those reported in Marie-Luce et al. (2024). In the framework of the SCINTI+ project, where the goal is to establish a reference method for scintillator-response measurements, larger coincidence resolving times may be required to accommodate slower scintillation kinetics.

These two factors—high single-channel rates and increased resolving times—lead to higher accidental-coincidence contributions. Therefore, accurate correction of accidental coincidences is essential, particularly in this configuration where physically useful coincidences occur with low probability.

3. Results

Application of experimental and analytical methods.

Measurements were performed using UltimaGold[®] liquid scintillation cocktail, both with and without tritium. The results obtained with the experimental method are reported in Table 1 and Table 2 under the label "Expt.". Figure 1 shows the time-difference distribution for the *DG* channel. True coincidences are concentrated at short delays (below approximately 1000 ns), whereas the distribution at longer delays is dominated by accidental coincidences. Therefore, the interval 2000–2500 ns can be used as an "accidental-only" region. The experimental correction was obtained by applying Eq. 1 to this analysis window for the scintillator used in this experiment.

The same datasets were also processed with the in-house software, which provides the raw counting rates for all physical and logical channels. The analytical correction procedure described above was then applied to these rates. The corresponding results are reported in Table 1 and Table 2 under the label "Calc."

Comparison of experimental and analytical approaches.

Three acquisitions with different configuration have been registered, on each the two methods have been applied and compared together. The results obtained for TDCR corrected accidental coincidence using the formula from Dutsov et al. (2020) are also calculated. All acquisitions were processed using a 20 μs dead time, and the coincidence resolving time τ was varied from 40 to 3000 ns. Figure 4 shows the *DG* counting rate as a function of τ , normalized to the corrected value at the reference resolving time, together with the analytically corrected and experimentally corrected results for one representative acquisition. Analytical and experimental methods show great corrections despite raw data increasing with coincidence window. To compare quantitatively, Dutsov et al. (2020) introduced the Δ value as the quantitative difference between the two methods, N_{calc} being the accidental counting rate corrected with the analytical method and N_{expt} with the experimental method:

$$\Delta = N_{calc}/N_{expt} - 1 \quad (20)$$

Table 1 summarizes the counting rates corrected with both methods, the ratio of accidental coincidences over raw rate and the Δ value for a full vial of UG scintillator. For example, for a 100 ns coincidence window, accidental coincidences represent about 0.6% of the *DG* raw rate, and the corrected *DG* counting rates obtained with the two approaches are practically identical, leading to $\Delta \approx 0$. A noticeable difference is nevertheless observed for the accidental component itself ($\Delta = -5.4\%$), which is attributed to the very low accidental counting rates ($0.12184(7) \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the analytical method and $0.1288(39) \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the experimental method), for which relative statistical uncertainties are comparatively large.

For a much larger coincidence window (3000 ns), accidental coincidences account for 15.7% of the *DG* raw rate. Despite this substantial accidental contribution, the corrected *DG* counting rates remain in close agreement, with a relative difference of only about 0.3%. A small residual discrepancy is observed at the largest resolving time, which may reflect the increasing sensitivity of high-order coincidence channels to (i) higher-order accidental terms beyond the first-order ($O(\tau)$) approximation used in the analytical model and/or (ii) dead-time and large coincidence-time effects when operating at high single-channel rates and long resolving times. Overall, Δ was evaluated for each logical channel and for each resolving time, and the results demonstrate very good consistency between the experimental and analytical correction methods across the investigated range that is much larger than the one expected to be used with this method.

To increase the PMT counting rates and further test the methodology under more demanding conditions, two additional measurements were performed using UltimaGold[®] samples with tritium at two activity levels. Table 2 summarizes the accidental-coincidence rates and the corrected counting rates for the *D*, *T*, *DG*, and *TG* channels.

As observed previously, the Δ values obtained for the accidental components can appear relatively large. This effect is mainly driven by the very low accidental counting rates in the gamma-coincidence channels (*DG* and *TG*), for which small absolute differences translate into large relative deviations and the statistical uncertainties are comparatively high. In contrast, the corrected counting rates show very good agreement between the analytical and experimental approaches, confirming that both methods provide consistent corrections for the coincidence channels of interest.

4. Conclusion

Dutsov et al. (2020) derived analytical expressions to correct accidental coincidences in three-channel TDCR counting. In the present work, this framework was generalized to N -channel coincidence systems by combining an inclusion–exclusion decomposition of the measured logic rates into exclusive (pure) rates with a logic-level accidental model including a Type-1 (Jánossy creation) contribution and a Type-2 (pile-up) contribution. This step-wise formulation avoids the rapid growth of combination cross terms that occurs when attempting to write direct closed-form expressions for higher-dimensional coincidence logic.

The method was implemented and applied to a four-channel Compton-TDCR configuration (three PMTs plus one gamma channel) providing single, double, triple and quadruple coincidence rates. The analytical correction was compared with an experimental approach based on estimating accidental coincidences from an accidental-only region

Table 1

Comparison between analytical (Calc.) and experimental (Expt.) methods obtained for DG and TG accidental and true coincidence counting rates for different resolving time. The value a_i/n_i represents the relative contribution of the accidental counting rates a_i (calculated with the experimental method) over the total (corrected + experimental) counting rates n_i .

Resolv. time, ns	Corr. method	DG acc., s^{-1}	DG true, s^{-1}	TG acc., s^{-1}	TG true, s^{-1}
100	Calc.	0.12184 (7)	23.414 (13)	0.083985 (26)	9.266 (8)
	Expt.	0.1288 (39)	23.407 (13)	0.0913 (26)	9.259 (8)
	Δ	-5.4 %	0.0 %	8.1 %	0.1 %
	a_i/n_i		0.6 %		1.0 %
500	Calc.	0.62164 (34)	24.538 (13)	0.43889 (14)	9.949 (8)
	Expt.	0.644 (19)	24.516 (23)	0.457 (13)	9.931 (15)
	Δ	-3.5 %	0.1 %	-3.9 %	0.2 %
	a_i/n_i		2.6 %		4.6 %
1000	Calc.	1.2584 (7)	24.651 (13)	0.89643 (28)	10.006 (9)
	Expt.	1.288 (39)	24.622 (41)	0.913 (26)	9.989 (27)
	Δ	-2.3 %	0.1 %	-1.9 %	0.2 %
	a_i/n_i		5.2 %		9.1 %
2000	Calc.	2.5699 (14)	24.675 (14)	1.8588 (6)	9.974 (9)
	Expt.	2.58 (8)	24.67 (8)	1.83 (5)	10.01 (5)
	Δ	-0.3 %	0.0 %	1.8 %	0.3 %
	a_i/n_i		10.4 %		18.3 %
3000	Calc.	3.9288 (21)	24.594 (14)	2.8822 (9)	9.860 (10)
	Expt.	3.86 (12)	24.66 (12)	2.74 (8)	10.00 (8)
	Δ	1.7 %	-0.3 %	5.2 %	-1.4 %
	a_i/n_i		15.7 %		27.4 %

of the time-difference distributions (2000–2500 ns). Both approaches yielded consistent corrected coincidence rates for UltimaGold[®] samples with and without tritium.

The results indicate that the coincidence-window range of primary interest for Compton-TDCR operation is below about 1000 ns, where true coincidences dominate and the accidental contribution remains limited. In this region, the corrected *DG* and *TG* rates obtained by the analytical and experimental approaches agree within uncertainties, with differences on corrected rates at the 0.0–0.2% level for the conditions investigated. At larger resolving times (2000–3000 ns), the accidental fraction increases and small residual discrepancies between methods become more visible, which is consistent with the increased sensitivity of higher-order coincidence channels to higher-order accidental terms and/or dead-time effects at long resolving times. This limitation is not critical for the intended use of the method, since resolving times above 1000 ns correspond to a regime where coincidences are increasingly dominated by accidentals rather than by physically useful events.

Finally, the experimental correction remains robust over the full range investigated because accidental coincidences can be directly estimated from the accidental-only region, providing an independent validation of the analytical model. Overall, the proposed analytical method offers a practical and readily implementable correction procedure for multi-detector coincidence systems and supports the reliable use of Compton-TDCR for radionuclide and scintillator metrology.

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Table 2

Comparison between analytical (Calc.) and experimental (Expt.) methods obtained for D, T, DG and TG accidental and true coincidence counting rates for the three samples. All the counting rates are corrected at 100 ns resolving time. The value a_i/n_i represents the relative contribution of the accidental counting rates a_i (calculated with the experimental method) over the total (corrected + experimental) counting rates n_i .

Scinti.	Corr. Method	Corrected counting rates, s^{-1}			
		D	T	DG	TG
UG Full vial	Raw	9845.09 (15)	4802.25 (21)	23.535 (11)	9.350 (7)
	Calc. Dutsov	9833.70 (28)	4792.91 (19)	-	-
	Calc. this work	9833.68 (26)	4791.90 (18)	23.414 (13)	9.266 (8)
	Expt.	9834.17 (27)	4791.95 (19)	23.407 (13)	9.259 (8)
	Δ	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.1 %
	a_i/n_i	0.1 %	0.2 %	0.6 %	1.0 %
UG H3 (8 kBq)	Raw	11058.30 (22)	5436.90 (16)	19.456 (10)	8.006 (6)
	Calc. Dutsov	11046.45 (28)	5424.94 (19)	-	-
	Calc. this work	11046.43 (28)	5424.93 (19)	19.338 (12)	7.925 (7)
	Expt.	11046.54 (29)	5424.90 (20)	19.332 (12)	7.919 (8)
	Δ	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.1 %
	a_i/n_i	0.1 %	0.2 %	0.6 %	1.1 %
UG H3 (21 kBq)	Raw	18068.0 (18)	8527.9 (13)	18.27 (6)	7.606 (37)
	Calc. Dutsov	18040.6 (24)	8497.56 (17)	-	-
	Calc. this work	18040.5 (24)	8497.5 (17)	18.09 (8)	7.48 (5)
	Expt.	18042.1 (25)	8498.0 (18)	18.06 (8)	7.46 (5)
	Δ	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.1 %	0.3 %
	a_i/n_i	0.1 %	0.4 %	1.2 %	1.9 %

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alice Perret: Methodology, Analysis, Original Draft, Software, Measurements. **Íñigo de Loyola Chacartegui Rojo:** Methodology, Analysis, Review Draft, Software. **Christophe Dujardin:** Analysis, Review Draft, Data Curating. **Benoît Sabot:** Methodology, Analysis, Original Draft, Software, Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Software.

References

- Bouchard, J., Cassette, P., 2000. Mac3: an electronic module for the processing of pulses delivered by a three photomultiplier liquid scintillation counting system. *Applied Radiation and Isotopes* 52, 669–672. doi:10.1016/S0969-8043(99)00228-6.
- Broda, R., 2003. A review of the triple-to-double coincidence ratio (TDCR) method for standardizing radionuclides. *Applied Radiation and Isotopes* 58, 585–594. doi:10.1016/S0969-8043(03)00056-3.
- Campion, P.J., 1959. The standardization of radioisotopes by the beta-gamma coincidence method using high efficiency detectors. *The International Journal of Applied Radiation and Isotopes* 4, 232–248. doi:10.1016/0020-708X(59)90199-1.
- Collé, R., 2009. Radionuclidic standardization by primary methods: An overview. *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry* 280, 265–273. doi:10.1007/s10967-009-0509-5.
- Dutsov, C., Cassette, P., Mitev, K., Sabot, B., 2021. In quest of the optimal coincidence resolving time in TDCR LSC. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 987, 164846. doi:10.1016/j.nima.2020.164846.
- Dutsov, C., Cassette, P., Sabot, B., Mitev, K., 2020. Evaluation of the accidental coincidence counting rates in TDCR counting. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 977, 164292. doi:10.1016/j.nima.2020.164292.
- Houtermans, H., Miguel, M., 1962. 4π - β - γ coincidence counting for the calibration of nuclides with complex decay schemes. *The International Journal of Applied Radiation and Isotopes* 13, 137–142. doi:10.1016/0020-708X(62)90137-0.
- Jánossy, L., 1944. Rate of n-fold accidental coincidences. *Nature* 153, 165–165. doi:10.1038/153165a0.
- Jordanov, V., Cassette, P., Dutsov, C., Mitev, K., 2020. Development and applications of a miniature tdcr acquisition system for in-situ radionuclide metrology. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 954, 161202. doi:10.1016/j.nima.2018.09.037.

- Marie-Luce, R., Mai, P., Lerouge, F., Cheref, Y., Pierre, S., Sabot, B., Chaput, F., Dujardin, C., 2024. Real-time detection and discrimination of radioactive gas mixtures using nanoporous inorganic scintillators. *Nature Photonics* 18, 1037–1043. doi:10.1038/s41566-024-01507-x.
- Mitchell, A.C.G., 1948. The use of coincidence counting methods in determining nuclear disintegration schemes. *Reviews of Modern Physics* 20, 296–304. doi:10.1103/RevModPhys.20.296.
- Sabot, B., Dutsov, C., Cassette, P., Mitev, K., 2022. Performance of portable tdc systems developed at Ine-Inhb. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 1034, 166721. doi:10.1016/j.nima.2022.166721.
- Sabot, B., Dutsov, C., Cassette, P., Mitev, K., Hamel, M., Bertrand, G.H.V., Lebbou, K., Dujardin, C., 2024. A compact detector system for simultaneous measurements of the light yield non-linearity and timing properties of scintillators 14, 6960. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-57186-9.

Figure 1: Time distribution of logical sum of the double events (D) and the gamma channel G for 20 mL of UltimaGold in plastic vial (PE-PTFE) in the Compton-TDCR system. The distribution shows that after 1000 ns, counting rates are stable, meaning that the events are only accidental coincidences. The linear fit was adjusted after 1 μ s

Figure 2: Illustration of correlated and uncorrelated coincidence events for a 3-channel device. Blue dots represent the uncorrelated events (A, B, C). Green dots represent the correlation between two channels (AB, BC, AC). Yellow dot represents the correlation between the 3-channel (ABC).

Figure 3: Illustration of and uncorrelated coincidence events for a 4-channel device. Blue dots represent the uncorrelated events (A, B, C, G). Green dots represent the correlated events between two channels (AB, BC, AC, AG, BG, CG). Yellow dots represent the correlated event between three channels (ABC, ABG, BCG, ACG). Red dot represents the correlated events between the 4-channel (ABCG). (a) Represents a 3D-view with the normal plan that correspond to Fig.2. (b) unfolded view of (a) the red star represents the p_{ABCG} which can't be unfolded.

Figure 4: Counting rate in the DG-channel in function of the resolving time without and with correction of accidental coincidences. The correction was made with two methods : analytically (Calc.) and experimentally (Expt.). The counting rates are normalized by the corrected value at 1.6 μ s. The linear fit was adjusted after 800 ns.